

Prediction of lamination-induced colour changes using artificial neural networks and ICC-based colour transformation

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Abstract— This study developed an artificial neural network (ANN) to predict post-lamination spectral reflectance from pre-lamination reflectance data. A dataset of 4,455 colour samples was obtained from ECI 2002 targets printed on coated paper and laminated with a matte BOPP film. Spectral reflectance was measured before and after lamination over the wavelength range of 380–730 nm. The results showed that lamination produced colour-dependent spectral changes, including overall increases, decreases, and wavelength-dependent variations in reflectance. The ANN successfully learned this nonlinear transformation and predicted the colour appearance of laminated prints with high accuracy, achieving a mean colour difference of 1.12 ΔE^*ab . Only 6.95% of the 891 test samples exhibited colour differences greater than 2 ΔE^*ab . The ANN also showed slightly better performance than an ICC-based colour transformation, reducing the mean prediction error by approximately 7%. These findings demonstrate that ANN-based spectral modelling is a promising approach for predicting lamination-induced colour changes and supporting colour management in post-press finishing.

Keywords— Artificial neural network, colour prediction, lamination, ICC profile, spectral reflectance

I. INTRODUCTION

Film lamination is widely applied to printed products, particularly in packaging, to improve surface protection and modify the visual appearance of the print. Although laminating films are nominally transparent, the addition of a film and adhesive layer changes the optical boundary conditions at the print surface. External reflection at the air–film interface, transmission through the film, multiple internal reflections, and lateral light scattering within the print–film system can modify the measured spectral reflectance and, consequently, the perceived lightness, chroma, and hue of printed colours [1–6]. These colour changes may be large enough to affect colour matching, contract proofing, brand-colour reproduction, and process control. Therefore, predicting the final colour appearance after lamination is an important requirement for reliable colour management in print production.

Several approaches have been proposed to model colour changes caused by transparent surface finishing. Early studies primarily used analytical or empirical optical transformations. Simonot and Elias [1] established a relationship between the reflectance of an unvarnished diffusing surface and that of the same surface covered by a transparent varnish layer, accounting for reflections at the different optical interfaces. Hoffstadt [2] investigated glossy and matte varnishes as well as oriented polypropylene films applied to offset prints. The proposed simulation represented finishing-induced changes through additional tone-value increase and, for matte surfaces, an achromatic stray-light contribution. The transformed colour data were subsequently used to generate ICC profiles representing the finished printing condition.

More recent studies have developed physically based models specifically for halftone prints. Hébert et al. [3] showed that a transparent layer can alter the colour of a halftone by increasing the probability that laterally scattered light interacts with multiple printed and unprinted regions. This phenomenon is associated with repeated reflections between the printed substrate and the film–air interface and produces a ring-shaped light-spreading pattern, commonly described as a halo effect. Dailliez et al. [4] formulated a multi-convolutive reflectance model for single-ink line halftones covered by a smooth transparent layer and

experimentally evaluated the influence of coating thickness and halftone period. The same optical principle was subsequently combined with multispectral microscopy to predict the spatially resolved reflectance and the average spectral reflectance of coated halftones [5]. The model was later extended to transparent layers with matte surface finishing by introducing a microfacet-based description of the rough film–air interface [6]. Physically based approaches provide valuable insight into the mechanisms responsible for colour changes and can achieve good accuracy under controlled conditions. However, their practical application generally requires detailed information about the optical system, such as film thickness, refractive index, interface reflectance, surface roughness, halftone geometry, and spatial light-scattering behaviour. Some methods also require multispectral microscopic images or specially designed halftone patterns [4–6]. Consequently, transferring these models to industrial CMYK prints produced with different papers, inks, adhesives, film types, and screening conditions may require additional measurements, parameter estimation, or model recalibration.

In practical colour-management workflows, another approach is to represent the printed product after surface finishing as a separate characterised colour condition. FOGRA49 and FOGRA50, for example, provide ICC profiles for proofing the final appearance of sheet-fed offset prints laminated with matte or glossy OPP films [7]. Hoffstadt [2] further proposed a modified ICC-profile approach in which coated colour appearances were predicted by linking colourimetric data from coated and uncoated profiles through adjusted gradation curves. Such profile-based approaches are attractive because they can be integrated into conventional prepress workflows without explicitly modelling the physical light-scattering mechanisms within the laminate film. However, an ICC-based transformation is still tied to the specific printing and finishing condition used for characterisation. Its predictive accuracy may decrease when the actual print run, substrate, ink, adhesive, or laminate film differs from the condition represented by the profile. Moreover, because the profile operates through colourimetric characterisation and interpolation, it may not fully describe wavelength-dependent spectral changes caused by the laminate layer.

Data-driven modelling offers an alternative that does not require an explicit description of every optical interaction. Stiene et al. [7] compared a heuristic method with an artificial neural network for predicting lamination-induced spectral changes in UV offset prints. Their heuristic approach combined wavelength-dependent film transmission with the nominal area coverage of the CMYK separations, whereas the ANN learned a direct mapping between the 36-band reflectance spectra measured before and after lamination. The ANN achieved a mean prediction error of approximately 0.6 ΔE_{00} , compared with approximately 1.4 ΔE_{00} for the heuristic method [7]. These results demonstrated the potential of neural networks to capture nonlinear spectral transformations. However, the authors also noted that the trained network was valid only for the process parameters represented in the training data and that further validation was required for matte films, other substrates, and different printing and screening conditions.

The available literature therefore reveals a trade-off between the existing approaches. Physically based models are interpretable but require specialised optical parameters and measurement systems. ICC profiles are well established in industrial workflows but are tied to a defined characterisation condition and rely on lookup-table interpolation. Artificial neural networks can learn complex nonlinear transformations directly from measured data, but their performance for broad CMYK colour datasets and their practical advantage over conventional ICC characterisation remain insufficiently evaluated.

Accordingly, the present study develops an artificial neural network to predict the post-lamination spectral reflectance of offset-printed colours directly from their measured pre-lamination spectra. The investigation focuses on colour changes produced by matte BOPP film lamination over a broad range of CMYK colour combinations. To provide an industrially relevant benchmark, the ANN predictions are evaluated against measured laminated samples and compared with predictions obtained using a conventional ICC profile-based characterisation method. This comparison is intended to determine whether the ANN can reproduce the nonlinear spectral transformation caused by lamination more accurately than the ICC-based approach and to assess its potential for practical colour prediction and process control.

II. EXPERIMENTAL

A. Sample preparation

To investigate lamination-induced colour changes, a 1485-patch colour chart (ECI 2002 target, Fig. 1) was printed using a Heidelberg Speedmaster SM102-4 sheet-fed offset press with Apex-G process inks (CMYK) on coated paper (150 g/m²). The chart included a wide range of CMYK tonal combinations in order to represent the printable colour space. To incorporate normal printing variability and increase the size of the training dataset, the target was printed in three separate print runs under the same nominal printing conditions, resulting in a total of 4455 colour samples. After printing, the sheets were conditioned under ambient laboratory conditions prior to further processing.

The printed sheets were subsequently laminated using a thermal lamination process. A 25 µm biaxially oriented polypropylene (BOPP) matte film was applied as the laminating material. The film was bonded to the printed surface using an FM-380 laminating machine operated at 120 ± 2 °C, allowing the laminate film to bond to the printed surface. The process was performed under uniform operating conditions to ensure consistent treatment of all colour patches.

Fig. 1 ECI 2002 Characterization Target

B. Color measurement

Colour measurements were performed using a Myro-1 spectrophotometer (Konica Minolta) under D50 illumination with a 2° CIE standard observer. The reflectance of each colour patch was recorded over the wavelength range from 380 nm to 730 nm with a sampling interval of 10 nm, resulting in 36 wavelength bands. Measurements were carried out both before and after lamination, providing paired datasets describing the original printed colours and the corresponding laminated colours. The paired spectral data served as the basis for both the ANN and ICC-based prediction models.

For colour evaluation, the measured and predicted reflectance values were converted to CIE XYZ tristimulus values and subsequently transformed into CIELAB colour coordinates (L*, a*, b*). Prediction accuracy was assessed by comparing predicted and measured CIELAB values of the laminated samples. Colour differences were calculated using the CIE 1976 colour difference formula (ΔE^*_{ab})

$$\Delta E^*_{ab} = \sqrt{\Delta L^{*2} + \Delta a^{*2} + \Delta b^{*2}} \quad (1)$$

where ΔL^* , Δa^* , and Δb^* represent the differences between the predicted and measured values of L*, a*, and b*, respectively

C. Artificial Neural Network (ANN)-based colour prediction

An artificial neural network (ANN) model was developed to predict the reflectance spectra of printed samples after lamination. The model was trained to learn the relationship between the spectra measured before lamination and the corresponding spectra after lamination.

The input variables consisted of 36 reflectance values measured before lamination in the wavelength range from 380 nm to 730 nm, while the output layer predicted the corresponding 36 reflectance values after lamination. Prior to training, the input and output datasets were standardised using separate StandardScaler models in order to improve the training stability of the network.

The ANN was implemented as a fully connected feed-forward neural network with three hidden layers. The complete dataset comprising 4455 colour samples was randomly divided into training (70%), validation (10%), and internal test (20%) subsets. The model was implemented in Python using the PyTorch framework. During training, the network weights were optimised using the Adam optimiser with a learning rate of 1×10^{-4} , while mean squared error (MSE) was used as the loss function. Training was performed for 1000 epochs with a batch size of 32. After training, the model was used to predict the reflectance spectra of laminated samples. The predicted spectra were subsequently converted to colour coordinates and evaluated following the procedure described in Section II.B. The architecture and training configuration of the ANN model are summarised in Table I

TABLE I
ARCHITECTURE AND TRAINING PARAMETERS OF THE ANN MODEL

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Network type	Fully connected feed-forward ANN	Activation function	ReLU
Input variables	36 reflectance values	Output variables	36 reflectance values
Spectral range	380–730 nm	Spectral interval	10 nm
Hidden layer 1	128 neurons	Hidden layer 2	128 neurons
Hidden layer 3	64 neurons	Output layer	36 neurons
Data preprocessing	StandardScaler (input/output)	Training approach	Supervised learning
Training samples	4455	Batch size	32
Optimiser	Adam	Learning rate	1×10^{-4}
Loss function	Mean squared error (MSE)	Training epochs	1000
Programming language	Python	Framework	PyTorch

D. ICC profile-based colour prediction

For comparison with the ANN model, an ICC-based colour transformation was generated using ArgyllCMS. In contrast to a conventional CMYK-to-Lab prediction workflow, this transformation was constructed from paired pre-lamination and post-lamination colour data. The pre-lamination CIELAB values were defined as the source condition, while the corresponding post-lamination values were used as the destination condition. This setup allowed the ICC method to estimate the laminated colour appearance from the actual colour state before lamination, providing a more comparable reference for the ANN model.

The resulting ICC transformation was applied to the independent test samples to predict their post-lamination CIELAB values. Prediction accuracy was then evaluated by comparing the predicted and measured laminated colours using ΔE^*_{ab} .

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Lamination-induced colour changes

The colour changes induced by matte BOPP lamination were investigated in detail in our previous study [8], including the effects of paper substrate and the respective contributions of lightness, chroma, and hue differences. The present section provides only a brief description of the colour-change characteristics represented in the modelling dataset, as the primary objective of this study is to evaluate colour prediction performance. For the 4455 colour samples included in the dataset, the mean colour difference between the un laminated and laminated prints was $6.46 \Delta E^*_{ab}$, while the median value was 6.13. The 90th percentile reached $10.49 \Delta E_{ab}$, indicating that a substantial proportion of the samples underwent visually significant colour changes. Overall, 88% of the samples exhibited colour differences greater than $3 \Delta E^*_{ab}$, and 63% exceeded $5 \Delta E^*_{ab}$. These results demonstrate that the dataset covers a broad range of lamination-induced colour shifts.

Representative spectral changes induced by lamination are shown in Fig. 2, where ΔR was calculated as the difference between the post-lamination and pre-lamination reflectance values at each wavelength ($\Delta R = R_{\text{post}} - R_{\text{pre}}$). Positive ΔR values indicate an increase in reflectance after lamination, whereas negative values indicate a decrease. The selected samples illustrate three characteristic responses observed in the dataset. For some colours, lamination produced an overall increase in reflectance across most of the visible spectrum, whereas other colours exhibited a general decrease. A third group showed wavelength-dependent behaviour, with reflectance increasing in certain spectral regions and decreasing in others. These results demonstrate that the effect of lamination is highly colour dependent and may influence both the overall reflectance level and the spectral shape of the printed colour. The diversity of spectral responses indicates that the transformation from pre-lamination to post-lamination reflectance cannot be adequately described by a simple offset or a uniform scaling factor. Instead, the relationship is nonlinear and depends on the initial spectral characteristics of each colour sample. Consequently, a data-driven model capable of learning complex spectral transformations is required. This consideration motivated the development of the ANN model described in the following section.

Fig. 2 Representative spectral changes ($\Delta R = R_{\text{post}} - R_{\text{pre}}$) induced by lamination

B. Development and internal validation of the ANN model

An artificial neural network (ANN) was developed to predict the post-lamination reflectance spectra from the measured spectra of un laminated prints. As described in Section II.C, the dataset consisting of 4,456 colour samples was randomly divided into training (70%), validation (10%), and internal test (20%) subsets. The internal test set ($n = 891$) was used to evaluate the prediction performance of the model within the colour space represented by the ECI 2002 chart.

The training and validation loss curves are presented in Fig. 3. Both losses decreased rapidly during the initial training stage and gradually converged to stable values after approximately 20 epochs. The close agreement between the training and validation curves throughout the training process indicates that the model successfully learned the spectral transformation induced by lamination without evident overfitting. The stable convergence behaviour suggests good generalization within the colour space covered by the training dataset.

Fig. 3 Training and validation loss curves of the ANN model during training

The prediction performance of the ANN on the internal test set is summarized in Table II. The model achieved low colour differences between the predicted and measured post-lamination colours, demonstrating its ability to accurately reproduce the spectral changes caused by the lamination process. Most test samples exhibited small prediction errors, while only a very small fraction of the dataset showed large colour differences. Specifically, only 0.78% of the test samples presented ΔE^*_{ab} values greater than 5, indicating that large prediction errors were relatively uncommon.

TABLE III
PREDICTION PERFORMANCE OF THE ANN MODEL ON THE INTERNAL TEST SET (N = 891 SAMPLES)

Metrics	ANN
Mean ΔE^*_{ab}	1.12
Median ΔE^*_{ab}	0.89
90th percentile ΔE^*_{ab}	7.61
Maximum ΔE^*_{ab}	32.14
% $\Delta E^*_{ab} > 2$	6.95
% $\Delta E^*_{ab} > 5$	0.78

Representative spectral predictions corresponding to the 10th, 50th, and 98th percentiles of the colour-difference distribution are shown in Fig. 4. For the 10th-percentile sample ($\Delta E^*_{ab} = 0.41$) and the median sample ($\Delta E^*_{ab} = 0.89$), the predicted spectra almost completely overlapped the measured post-lamination spectra across the visible wavelength range. Even for the 98th-percentile sample ($\Delta E^*_{ab} = 3.16$), the ANN successfully reproduced the overall spectral profile, although noticeable deviations were observed over a broad wavelength region. These results indicate that the model effectively captured the non-linear spectral transformation associated with lamination and was able to reproduce both the spectral shape and the resulting colour appearance for the majority of samples within the training distribution.

Although a small number of outliers with substantially larger colour differences were observed in the internal test set, these samples represented only a minor fraction of the overall dataset. Therefore, the internal validation results demonstrate that the ANN provides an accurate spectral prediction framework for modelling lamination-induced colour changes within the colour space represented by the training data.

Fig. 4 Representative ANN spectral predictions for samples corresponding to the 10th, 50th, and 98th percentiles of the colour-difference distribution in the internal test set

To assess the practical applicability of the model, a more challenging evaluation was subsequently performed using an independent set of 84 colour samples that were not included in the training process. The predictive performance of the ANN was then compared with that of the ICC-based approach, as discussed in the following section.

C. Comparison of ICC- and ANN-based colour prediction

The prediction performances of the ICC-based and ANN-based approaches on the independent test set are summarized in Table III. Both methods achieved comparable prediction accuracy, indicating that lamination-induced colour changes can be effectively modelled using either a conventional colour-transformation approach or a data-driven spectral prediction model. Nevertheless, the ANN consistently produced slightly lower prediction errors. The mean and median colour differences were reduced from 3.49 and 2.39 ΔE_{ab} for the ICC-based method to 3.25 and 2.14 ΔE_{ab} , respectively, while the percentages of samples exceeding 3 ΔE_{ab} and 5 ΔE_{ab} were also marginally lower.

TABLE III
PREDICTION PERFORMANCE OF ICC AND ANN (N = 84 SAMPLES)

Metrics	ICC	ANN	Difference (ANN-ICC)
Mean ΔE^*_{ab}	3.49	3.25	-0.24
Median ΔE^*_{ab}	2.39	2.14	-0.25
90th percentile ΔE^*_{ab}	7.02	7.17	0.15
Maximum ΔE^*_{ab}	19.38	15.37	-4.01
% $\Delta E^*_{ab} > 3$	38.1	35.7	-2.4
% $\Delta E^*_{ab} > 5$	21.4	20.2	-1.2

The similar overall performance of the two approaches suggests that a properly constructed ICC transformation based on measured pre-lamination and post-lamination data can provide effective prediction of laminated colour appearance. However, the ANN offers several advantages. As shown in Section III-A, lamination may produce complex spectral changes, including increases, decreases, or wavelength-dependent variations in reflectance. By learning the relationship between the complete pre-lamination and post-

lamination reflectance spectra, the ANN can model these nonlinear transformations directly rather than relying on interpolation within a colourimetric lookup table.

In addition, the applicability of the two approaches differs considerably. The ICC transformation is established for a specific combination of printing and lamination conditions, and changes in substrate, ink set, laminate film, or process conditions may require the generation of a new profile to maintain prediction accuracy. In contrast, the ANN framework can be extended by incorporating additional training data from different materials and production conditions. Although the improvement in prediction accuracy observed in this study was modest, the ANN provides a flexible and scalable approach for developing generalized colour-prediction models for laminated printed products.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This study evaluated ANN-based prediction of colour changes induced by matte BOPP lamination and compared it with an ICC-based colour transformation. Lamination produced complex, colour-dependent spectral changes that could not be represented by a simple common correction.

The ANN learned the relationship between pre-lamination and post-lamination reflectance spectra and predicted laminated colour appearance with good accuracy. Its performance was comparable to, and slightly better than, the ICC-based method. Although the improvement was modest, the ANN offers greater flexibility because it can be extended with additional training data from different substrates, inks, films, and process conditions.

Overall, ANN-based spectral prediction provides a viable and scalable approach for modelling lamination-induced colour shifts in printed products

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